

PREDICTION OF LONG-TERM BEHAVIOR OF FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies prediction of long-term behavior of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP), including thermosetting and thermoplastic FRP, gives the estimation of creep properties and three extrapolation techniques to analyse the test data, and proposes a statistic analysis of long-term strength of FRP. The results of analyses and experiments obtained here could be used for designing products as well as researching on the behavior of FRP.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced plastics is a new engineering material, which is being used to an increasing extent in engineering practice. While composites exhibit many desirable mechanical properties, they also exhibit a few which are undesirable. One of these is that FRP possess creep phenomenon under room temperature and their rupture strength will reduce as the time increases. For the products and components which bear the long-term load such as boat, bridge, tank, pipe, pressure vessel, recreational equipment and various joints etc. life prediction is an important problem, i.e. "How long will they last?" In fact, this problem relates to both raw materials and their protection during their service process. Anywise one makes an attempt to predict long-term stiffness and strength as well as service life. All these need the data on creep properties and long-term strength. For the thermoplastic FRP developed in the past 20 years, this is also very important. This paper studies prediction of long-term behavior in consideration of the demand on design of products and development of new materials. So we carried out the researches on the properties of FRP commonly used in China.

CREEP BEHAVIOR

1. Creep Mechanism

Creep is a macroscopic phenomenon. The creep behavior of FRP is dominated by the matrix. Under a dead load, due to its relaxation behavior of high-elasticity, the matrix will generate creep deformation gradually. On the other hand, besides the organic fibre, the deformation of fibres is very small under room temperature. By the way, here we carried out a flexural creep test of brick-glass, which lasted for 1,200 hours and no creep occurred. Hence we may neglect the creep of fibres, when we analyse the creep properties.

2. Estimation of Creep Modulus

The creep modulus of FRP may estimate in terms of the creep moduli of its constitutional materials, and the rule-of-mixtures is still valid, but both moduli of fibre and matrix are time-dependent. If the modulus of matrix has been tested the creep modulus of composite can be estimated when fibre creep is neglected.

A. Continuous fibre reinforced composite.

For uniaxial tension, the expression of creep modulus calculated by the rule-of-mixtures in the fibre direction is

$$E(t) = E_1 V_1 + E_R(t)(1-V_f) \quad (1)$$

where $E(t)$ is creep modulus of composite at time t ; E_f is fibre modulus, which is time-independent; $E_r(t)$ is creep modulus of resin at time t and V_f is the fibre volume fraction. Meanwhile the approximate expression of the creep modulus in transverse direction is

$$E_r(t) = E_R/A_R \quad (2)$$

in which A_R is resin content of weight (%).

Eq.1 and Eq.2 may also be used for calculating creep moduli of fabric reinforced composites (see ref.1)

The flexural creep tests of some resin and FRP have been carried out, the tested value and estimated value of creep moduli of FRP is given in Table 1. Due to factors of fibre, matrix materials and forming art (for example, the deviation of the fibre direction), the tested values are lower than estimated ones.

Table 1 Creep moduli of three thermosetting FRP

Type of FRP	Stress ratio (%)	Temperature (C)	Creep moduli at following time (hrs)					
			1		10		100	
			Measured	Estimated	Measured	Estimated	Measured	Estimated
GF/E51	30	14	13.7	13.4	13.3	13.2	12.8	12.5
GF/E6828	30	20	14.7	14.6	14.2	14.4	14.0	14.2
GF/E-AFG	30	23	14.4	14.5	14.2	14.2	13.8	13.8

B. Short fibre reinforced thermoplastic materials.

These materials are considered as isotropic materials, and their creep moduli under simple tension are as follows:

$$E(t) = \frac{1}{6}E_fV_f + (1 - \frac{1}{6}V_f) E(t) \quad (3)$$

The Eq.3 can be used to estimate approximately the flexural creep moduli.

The flexural creep moduli of three kinds of thermoplastics, (which are polysulfone, polycarbonate and polypropylene,) and their composites reinforced by chopped glass fibre were measured. The tested and estimated values are shown in Table 2. For the complex state of stresses, we adopt the principle of superposition and use of regressive computation with computer².

3. Creep Data Analysis

The creep test period of composites is long and complex, so that the cost is higher. It requires an extrapolation method for estimating the long-term properties from the short, time data tested in order to get design data. The extrapolated result may be doubted, but it is a prerequisite for engineering practice. In general, it is required to carry out test for 1, 000 hours, and the last result may be extrapolated to the period of 105 hrs. We will introduce following three extrapolations.

A. Creep curve method ($\epsilon - \log_{10}t$)

The creep law at stable stage may be expressed in the form

$$\epsilon(t) = \epsilon'_0 + V_0 \cdot \log_{10}t \quad (4)$$

Table 2 Creep modulus ratio between one at time t and their original's for 3 thermoplastic FRP

Type of FRP	Stress ratio (%)	Temperature (°C)	Resin content (%)	$E(t)/E(0)$ at following time (hrs.)					
				1		10		100	
				Measured	Estimated	Measured	Estimated	Measured	Estimated
GF/pp	30	20	74.4	0.89	0.88	0.81	0.81	0.73	0.74
GF/pc	30	20	82.5	0.97	0.97	0.95	0.94	0.90	0.89
GF/ps	30	20	80.7	0.97	0.98	0.95	0.96	0.92	0.93

When this method is used, we plot the creep curve $\epsilon - \log_{10} t$ during a short time (see Fig.1), and extend the line BC to intersect the axis of ϵ at A', and the another end extend to F. The creep moduli at point of line CF are predicted by Eq.(4), where constants ϵ_0 and V_0 can be obtained from the curve $\epsilon - \log_{10} t$. As usual, the creep moduli are needed in structural design. The corresponding evolution equation may have the form

$$E(t) = E(1) / (1 + D \log_{10} t) \quad (5)$$

in which $E(1)$ is creep modulus at the first hour, and D is equal to v_0 / ϵ_0'

Fig.1 Sketch of the estimation using typical creep curve

B. Logarithmic-hyperbolic method.

The equation-fitting [3] is a logarithmic-hyperbola with three-arbitrary coefficients,

$$E(t) = (A + B \log_{10} t) / (1 + C \log_{10} t) \quad (6)$$

where A, B and C are arbitrary constants selected to fit observed data as best as it can.

C. Exponential curve method.

The equation-fitting selected is in expression:

$$\log_{10}(J_0 - \log_{10} E) = M + N \log_{10} T \quad (7)$$

where M and N are constants. Pick out data 15 to 25 points as for paired time and modulus, calculate two constants M and N using a least mean squares. The author provides with utility BASIC computer program, and analysed more than 100 data of thermosetting composite specimens. From above analysis, we derived following conclusions: for the creep moduli of resin cast and glass reinforced epoxy and unsaturated polyester, the last measurements are extrapolated to ten times of the time, their errors are about 10% and 5% respectively.

The difference between Eq.6 and Eq.5 is to add the $\log_{10} t$ term to the numerator of Eq.6. As time t approaches ∞ , their asymptotic curve is different, former's is line $E(\infty) = 0$, and latter's is line $E(\infty) = B/C$. Obviously, Eq.5 is more appropriate to resin cast, while Eq.6 is more appropriate to FRP. An example for the comparison of three methods is given in Fig.2

From Fig.2 we know the three curve-fittings approach the test data when the time t is larger than one hour, while t is less than one hour, Eq.7 is more close with the test data than the others (Eq.5 and Eq.6).

In a word, these three methods all can be used. The Eq.5 is more simple. Eq.6 is also convenient, and Eq.7 is the best, although it is more complex.

Fig.2 Curve-fittings of creep data using the three methods to analyse GF/UP-307

LONG-TERM STRENGTH

1. Character of Long-term Strength (LTS)

The load-bearing capacity of FRP obviously depends upon time, even the strength of glass fibre doesn't depend on time, the strength of composites still depends on time, because glass fibres bond with resin which transfers load from one fibre to another, while transferred magnitude is related to viscoelasticity of resin. The creep rupture test time is also very long. In general, it requires more than 3,000 hrs. The "short time strength" (STS) of FRP scatters larger, from 8% to 17% for uniaxial and quasi-isotropic FRP. Because of the scattering strength of fibre and resin as well as effect of forming factors, the LTS scatter more strongly than the STS as the time increases.

2. Data Analysis

In view of minor test of LTS, after ten years the strength is about half of the original value. Within 50-100% of the original value, more than 10 stress levels were chosen, and the flexural LTS test were carried out. Under constant temperature, The LTS σ at certain time and the corresponding time T to failure can be written in a simple relationship:

$$\sigma^n T = K \quad (8)$$

in which n is slope on the bilogarithmic curve of the LTS, T is the time to failure, and K is a constant, Eq.8 has another form:

$$\log_{10} \sigma = -\frac{1}{n} \log_{10} T + \frac{1}{n} \log_{10} K \quad (9)$$

When the accuracy of LTS are included, Eq.9 becomes:

$$\log_{10} \sigma = -\frac{1}{n} \log_{10} T + \frac{1}{n} \log_{10} K \pm 2S \quad (10)$$

where S is standard deviation.

An example is given in Fig.3. The flexural LTS of 5 thermosetting FRP have been carried out. The information on specimens is shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Constituent, number and size for 5 FRP

	GF/E-AFG	GF/E51	GF/UP-307	GF/UP-189	GF*/UP-189
Resin type	AFG-90Epoxy	E51Epoxy	307Polyester	189Polyester	189Ployester
Glass fibre and its lay-up	0.2Twill, cross lay-up of warp and woof			Glass cloth of Chopped strand 800g/M ² mat of 450g/M ²	
Resin content%	52.9	53.8	52.3	41.7	70.8
specimen Number	27	80	50	51	46
Size(mm)	80x15x3.8	80x15x4.0	80x15x3.8	100x15x4.0	100x15x4.0

Fig.3 σ - t curve-fitting plotted by Eq.10

All parameters of the equation-fittings for the five kinds of FRP are given in Table 4, the LTS value calculated by curve-fittings and the decrease percent is shown in Table 5. From Table 4 and Table 5 we know:

A. The value n ranges between 20 to 30 for the thermosetting FRP when the forming quality of specimen is good, which is almost coincident with that obtained by the high-speed load and common test, while the value n is more than 10 for the mat-reinforced laminates and for some thermosetting FRP of which specimen quality is poor.

Table 4 Parameters of equation-fittings for five FRP

Parameters	GF/E-AFG	GF/E-51	GF/UP-307	GF/UP-189	GF*/UP-189
n	29.9	25.1	20.5	12.5	11.9
$\log_{10}K$	75.1	61.8	51.4	35.6	24.3
S	0.0328	0.0329	0.0348	0.1040	0.0598

Table 5 The LTS values calculated by curve-fittings and their decrease

Time (hrs.)	GF/E-AFG			GF/E-51			GF/UP-307			GF/UP-189			GF*/UP-189		
	σ (Mpa)	ϕ (%)	Δ (%)												
0	375	0		340	0		376	0		319	0		179	0	
1	324	14		292	14		319	15		288	10		110	38	
10	300	20	± 16	267	21	± 17	285	24	± 17	240	25	± 38	91	49	± 24
100	276	26		243	29		255	32		209	37		75	58	
1000	256	32		222	35		228	39		166	48		62	65	
10000	237	37		202	40		204	46		138	57		51	72	

B. The LTS of GF/E-AFG, GF/E-51 and GF/UP-189 are more than half of their original strengthes, GF*/UP-189's approaches half of its original strength, and the LTS of mat-reinforced laminate decrease sharp, here only reserves 30% of its original value after 10^4 hrs.

C. The LTS has larger deviation.

The LTS relative errors for the all FRP are about 20%.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

From above analysis we may conclude:

The creep moduli of FRP can be predicted by the rule-of-mixtures which relates with time factors.

The design data may be obtained in time using the three extrapolated methods here. The long-term strength also can be predicted using Eq.8, which has another form:

$$\sigma_0^n T_0 = \sigma^n T \quad (11)$$

As analyzed above, the parameters n , σ_0 , and T_0 are obtained from test data, then the LTS at any time t will be obtained using Eq.11.

In a word, the long-term properties of FRP including creep modulus and long-term strength can be predicted.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author would like to thank Professor Zhu Yilin to go over this manuscript and make suggestions for revision.

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